

Teachers' Welfare as Determinants of Students Learning Outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial District

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ABSTRACT: The study examined teachers' welfare as determinants of students' learning outcomes in Junior Secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial District. The study had a sample size of 364 participants, and the instruments employed were the teachers' welfare questionnaire and the mathematics BECE). An estimate of dependability, using the Cronbach alpha approach, was obtained, and the resulting reliability index was 0.78. The research questions were addressed by calculating the coefficient of determination using Pearson's product moment correlation. Based on this data, it was determined that there is a favorable association between teacher welfare, decent salary payment, teacher advancement, and teacher incentives and student learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State. A joyful teacher with first-class welfare package will increase their drive which will aid good outcome. Based on the study findings, it was recommended that teachers' welfare should be prioritized to sustain learning outcome of pupils due to high decline in teachers population, Educational stakeholders should prioritize teachers' welfare as an indispensable factor that power students learning outcome in schools, car and housing loans should be made available to teachers to encourage the present and future generations to take teaching as a first choice.

KEYWORDS: Teacher; Welfare, Determinants, Student Learning Outcome, Junior Secondary Schools

INTRODUCTION

Education remains a critical tool for developing the capacity of citizens in every country (Boateng et al., 2020). As a result, the government's efforts to provide inclusive and equitable learning outcomes that promote lifelong opportunities for everyone should be a major commitment for attaining the new Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). The country parades a massive out-of-school youngsters and young adults who lack basic literacy and numeracy abilities. The goals of education are taken into consideration when evaluating the program's results. Academic achievement (sometimes expressed as test scores, but more frequently and widely in terms of exam performance) and other aspects of student growth, such as changes in attitudes, values, and creative and emotional expression, can also be evaluated, and behaviour have been devised (Education for All: EFA Global Monitoring Report, 2005). Human resources, on the other hand, are a crucial weapon in achieving educational goals because goals can only be accomplished via the collaborative efforts of instructors in a certain school structure. Shabbir et al, (2014), asserted that education is essential for human capital formation as the quality of a country's human resources is determined by its education system. According to studies, the greatest valuable asset in every firm, in public or commercial, is its people resources.

Teachers, as the human resources factor in this study, are thus critical to the success/attainment of students' learning outcomes, and when this critical tools or means is not appropriately planned, for example, in relation to welfare package, the quality of school products, which are learners' educational outcomes, becomes an illusion. According to Ejiofor and Mbachu (2011), Without educators, educational institutions merely consist of physical structures, landscaping, and technological devices. No other aspect is as vital as the teacher in ensuring corporate stability, progress, and goal achievement in the school organization, whether in the long or short term. Adelabu's (2015) study found that instructors in both public and private schools are undermotivated and unsatisfied with their salaries and work circumstances. Job environment, job contentment, and incentive system are the three primary categories into which many factors causing learners to have poor learning outcomes fall (Adelabu, 2015).

While many Nigerian schools go without basic amenities like bathrooms, Adelabu paints the picture of the work environment as a hodgepodge of dilapidated buildings. Teachers are overworked and unhappy, while pupils are hungry and unhappy at school. This type of learning environment does not foster high job morale, which promotes positive learning outcomes among students. Adelabu went on to say that job workload/content includes completely overworked teachers. On five days a week, the average government school teacher is expected to teach six or seven periods to classes with around fifty students each. Additional school-related tasks that these educators are required to assist with might be time-consuming and physically demanding. Promotion, bonus packages,

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and other salary-based incentives don't seem to be designed to motivate employees to do a good job. Students may falsify their results on assessments if teachers are not adequately compensated by the government (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023).

The main conclusions of a study conducted by Kazeem in Adelabu (2015) indicate that teachers and other school staff generally experience satisfaction and moderate levels of motivation when they receive their salary punctually and are promoted regularly. Isaac et al. (2023) determined that income, allowance, and promotion are the main elements that affect teacher views towards their employment. Igabari and Okagbare (2023) argue that a significant challenge facing Nigeria's teaching profession is the inadequate remuneration and irregular salary disbursements. Practicing educators prioritise timely wage disbursements and the provision of fringe or marginal benefits over other non-financial motivators. School principals habitually expressed discontent with teachers who were hesitant to work or put in any time as a result of delays in obtaining their salary (Ayeni, 2005). Ubom (2002) discovered that the swift payment of salaries in Nigeria led to a higher level/degree of commitment to the teaching occupation/profession. The establishment of the 1972 Udoji Commission, had a significant bearing on Nigerian teachers' welfare and status. The Commission effectively accomplished the standardisation of public sector remuneration by integrating all public sector personnel into a unified wage framework, so ensuring that teachers were at the same compensation level as other significant public sector workers.

The Commission proposed the implementation of a standardised system for evaluating and compensating public employees, including educators, to guarantee that the government can attract and retain an appropriate number of qualified personnel, while also addressing the issue of unequal pay discrepancies between private sectors and public sectors and. Nevertheless, the Commission's ambitious idea has been rejected by future governments, prompting teachers to request the National Union of Teachers for a more just and balanced assessment, compensation, and ranking of teachers compared to professionals in other fields (Adelabu, 2015).

Rousseau (2012) emphasised that discontentment within the educational profession has negative implications for students. There is an increasing amount of evidence indicating that when teachers are content with their profession, the educational achievements of children improve. Oluwadamilare (2012) reported that teacher motivation is an imperative aspect that results to successes and self-satisfaction, which lessens or reduces the incidence of teachers absenteeism and productivity/output. The teaching profession in Nigeria has gone from being everyone's envy to a laughingstock due to low salaries in recent years, and as a result, few young people are interested in becoming teachers and even fewer in secondary school. Paying a living wage will greatly enhance the dedication and performance of low-income earning teachers, according to Akinwunmi (as reported by Egbebi et al., 2018).

It is anticipated that the impact of "this development" will result in favorable or bad performance in students' learning achievement. According to the literature, elements such as society, school, family, and motivational factors all influence students' learning outcomes. For today's youth to flourish, learning outcomes are equally essential. Additionally, studies have shown that high-achieving students have an easier time adjusting to adulthood and achieving professional and financial success. Similarly, intrinsic motivation is a key factor in effective classroom management. Ololube (2014) observed that higher teacher motivation leads to increased teacher effectiveness, which benefits the educational system. Egbebi et al. (2018) evaluated teachers' well-being as a predictor of students' scholarly progress in primary schools. The findings demonstrated that teachers' well-being has a considerable impact on students' academic progress. If the teaching occupation or profession and the educational system are to endure, Ilunor (2010) argues that teacher welfare should be considered a valid incentive or motivation. Problems with teacher salary and compensation, including delays, inconsistencies, and errors, have significantly interfered with classroom activities involving students' decisions/judgement and management (Ofoegbu, 2001).

Egbebi et al. (2018) found that teachers are underpaid, undersupported, and underappreciated despite the importance of their work in the classroom (Egbebi et al, 2018). If put into place properly, free housing, healthcare, education for teachers' children, and Car loans, would act as accelerators to improve teacher classroom effectiveness. Poor salary and social conditions for teachers have resulted in the widespread proverb that 'teachers' rewards are above the earth' (Igabari & Okagbare, 2023).

RQs

1. What is the relationship between teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?
2. What is the relationship between good salary payment of teachers and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?
3. What is the relationship between teachers' promotion and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?
4. What is the relationship between teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?

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METHOD

This study utilized the correlational research approach. The study population comprises of 49200 (3500 teachers and 45700 students) in all the government owned secondary schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State. The study's sample size is 364 according to Krejcie and Morgan, as stated by Dikoru (2020). In Krejcie and Morgan's statistics table, the sample size for a population of 7000 or more is 364. This is enough for a 0.05 confidence level. This statistical table was utilized to ensure that the study's population yielded a manageable sample size. The study's sample was selected using a proportionate stratified random sampling approach/method, which took into account the ownership of schools (public/government or private). The study's sample was drawn using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique based on school proprietorship/ownership (public or private). Using the stratification, twelve (12) schools, which form 8% of the entire public school system, and sixteen (16) schools, which constitute 5% of the entire private school system, were picked, resulting in a total of 28 schools that were used. A simple random selection process was utilised to pick 13 teachers and pupils from the chosen schools, consisting of 7 female and 6 male teachers/students. The instruments used for this study was teachers' welfare questionnaire and mathematics BECE scores. The questionnaire has two sections: demographic data on teachers' welfare characteristics of gender. Section B focused on: Teachers' welfare (Teachers' prompt salary payment; Teachers' fringe benefits; Teachers' in-service-training; and Teachers' incentives). The instrument was of 4-point Likert scale questionnaire that focused on Teachers' Welfare. The questionnaire's validity was validated by three specialists in the Guidance and Counselling Department's Measurement and Evaluation Unit. The specialists evaluated the instruments to determine if they were suitable and appropriate for the study, and any recommendations they made were addressed. The instrument reliability was conducted with test-re-test. The teachers' welfare questionnaire was given to 20 senior secondary school teachers in Delta South. After a week interval the instrument was administered again to check the level of internal consistency of the instrument. The results of Cronbach Alpha yielded 0.78 which reflected a sound psychometric property of the instrument. All the research questions were answered using Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMCC) and coefficient of determination.

RESULTS

RQ1: What is the relationship between teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?

Table 1. PPMC Coefficient on the teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes

Model	N	r	R ²	Adjusted R Square	Remark
Teachers' Welfare					
Students learning Outcome	364	0.543	0.295	29.5	Positive Relationship

Table 1 showed the result of a correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to ascertain the association between teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes. The results revealed an r-value of 0.543 and an r²-value of 0.295. The results further showed that teachers' welfare contributed 29.5% to the variability in students learning outcomes (Math BECE) in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts. This implies a positive association between teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes.

RQ2: What is the relationship between good salary payment of teachers and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?

Table 2. PPMC Coefficient on good salary payment of teachers and students learning outcomes

Variable	N	R	r ²	r ² %	Decision
Good salary payment of teachers					
Students learning Outcome	364	0.417	0.174	17.4	Positive Relationship

Table 2 showed the result of a correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to ascertain the relationship between good salary payment of teachers and students learning outcomes. The results revealed an r-value of 0.417 and an r²-value of 0.174. The results further showed that good salary payment of teachers contributed 17.4% to the variability in students learning outcomes (Math BECE). This implies a positive association between good salary payment of teachers and students learning outcomes.

RQ3: What is the relationship between teachers' promotion and students learning outcome in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?

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Table 3. PPMC Coefficient on teachers' promotion and students learning outcomes

Variable	N	R	r ²	r ² %	Decision
teachers' promotion					
Students learning Outcome	364	0.593	0.352	35.2	Positive Relationship

Table 3 showed the result of a correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to ascertain the relationship between teachers' promotion and students learning outcomes. The results revealed an r-value of 0.593 and an r²-value of 0.352. The results further showed that teachers' promotion contributed 35.2% to the variability in students learning outcomes (Math BECE). This implies a positive correlation between teachers' promotion and students learning outcomes.

RQ 3: What is the relationship between teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools in Delta South Senatorial Districts of Delta State?

Table 4. PPMC Coefficient on teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes

Variable	N	R	r ²	r ² %	Decision
teachers' incentives					
Students learning Outcome	364	0.602	0.362	36.2	Positive Relationship

Table 4 showed the result of a correlation and coefficient of determination, which was used to ascertain the relationship between teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes. The results revealed an r-value of 0.602 and an r²-value of 0.362. The results further showed that teachers' incentives contributed 36.2% to the variability in students learning outcomes (Math BECE). This implies a positive relationship between teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Relationship between teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes in Junior Secondary Schools

The first finding revealed that there is a positive association/relationship between teachers' welfare and students learning outcomes. The findings indicated that teachers when encouragement, praised or appraised and strengthened morally, physically, socially among others ensured and inclusive learning outcome of students. The findings implied that teachers were being denied adequate welfare package to better their life which will in turn affect pupils' learning outcome positively. This study aligned with the study of Egbebi, et al (2018) who all posited that in-service training of teachers positively influences the academic outcome of students when government prioritize teachers' professional skills and knowledge morally, physically and socially.

Relationship between good salary payment of teachers and students' learning outcomes

The second finding revealed that there is a positive relationship between good salary payment of teachers and students learning outcomes. Prompt and good salary payment improves teachers' general well-being and act as motivation to improve service delivery and influences students learning outcomes in both private and government owned schools. This study corroborates the findings of Egbebi (2018), which revealed that low-income teachers desire a substantial salary increase. Consequently, it can be inferred that providing a liveable wage will greatly improve their dedication and effectiveness. The findings also agreed with Ubom's (2002) study, which discovered that in Nigeria, timely salary payments increased dedication to teaching.

Relationship between teachers' promotion and students' learning outcomes

The third finding revealed that there is a positive relationship between teachers' promotion and students learning outcomes. The findings indicated that promotion is an extrinsic factor that provide encourage to employees to maximally perform their duties. This study aligned with the study of Isaac et al (2023) identified promotion as the key factors that shape teacher attitudes towards their work and this of course boost students learning situation.

Relationship between teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes

The fourth finding revealed that there is a positive relationship between teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes. The indicated that fringe benefits like car and housing loan, health care in schools boot the learning outcome of students. When teachers are satisfied with their work or job, students' learning outcomes improves. This study aligned with the study of Marques (2010) who posited that motivation, satisfaction and performance are interdependent stating that teachers benefit from fringe asides their regular salaries are bound to improve pupils' learning outcome.

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CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained from this investigation, the subsequent deductions were made: that a positive relationship between teachers' welfare, good salary payment, teachers' promotion and teachers' incentives and students learning outcomes exists. And that a joyful teacher with first-class welfare scheme and package will enhance their drive and result to good output and outcome.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Teachers welfare should be prioritized to sustain learning outcome of pupils due to high decline in teachers population
2. Educational stakeholders should prioritize teachers' welfare as an indispensable factor that power students learning outcome in schools
3. Housing and Car/auto loans should be made available to teachers to encourage the present and future century generation to take teaching as a first choice
4. Teachers' salaries should be promptly and regularly increased and paid at a satisfactory level to have a positive impact on students' learning outcome.

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